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D.5.2 Principles on Data structuration and interfacing with EOSC

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Abstract

D5.2 "Principles on Data Structuration and Interfacing with EOSC" is a key component within Work Package 5 (WP5) of the IPERION-HS project. WP5 is dedicated to developing innovative methods and tools for managing and analysing complex data from heritage science and humanities. The deliverable directly addresses the challenge of integrating heterogeneous data sources related to these domains. This data is essential for research, conservation, and scientific analysis in disciplines such as history, art history, archaeology and philology.

To achieve this integration, the project has fostered close collaboration with data providers platforms, enabling better access to diverse digital assets (knowledge bases, datasets, procedures) and facilitating the development of innovative strategies to foster interoperability. D5.2 has focused on enhancing the description of data related to artifacts, not only through conventional metadata but also by capturing the entire scientific workflow from raw data to interpretation.

As data is increasingly important for scientific discoveries, simple rules (SQARED principles) were created within the scope of this project to help researchers better organize their data. Well organized data is crucial for scientific discoveries to remain useful in the long term and can be shared and better understood by other scientists.

WP5 members followed an experimental approach with the aim of facilitating the development of data management strategies based on the concept of overlapping "regions of interest" and creating bridges between different disciplines and data production contexts.

The result of this theoretical effort will be the development of mechanisms for integrating data, annotations, vocabulary terms, and other relevant attributes linked to these resources as part of D5.6 Prototype studies on Data structuration and interfacing with EOSC, also building on past and ongoing initiatives such as ARIADNE, IPERION CH, PARTHENOS, SSHOC, and ARIADNE+ and aligning with relevant international standards and organizations like EOSC, RDA, and DARIAH ERIC.

Narrative (technical) description

1. Introduction

In Cultural and Scientific Heritage research, data provides the essential evidence for establishing and refining scientific understanding, foster collaboration, and drive innovation. However, the vast and diverse nature of CH data, often originating from disparate sources and adhering to varying formats and standards, poses significant challenges for effective integration and utilization. To achieve a high level of data integrity that fosters discoverability, accessibility, and reusability, a two-part approach is required:

- **Ontology selection/modelling:** At the heart of a strong data structure lies a well-defined ontology. The ontology works as a controlled vocabulary for researchers, defining a consistent set of classes (representing entities or concepts) and properties (representing characteristics) specific to the cultural heritage domain. This ensures all data adheres to a shared schema, facilitating seamless interoperability and collaboration amongst researchers by eliminating ambiguity and ensuring consistent data representation.
- **Guiding Principles:** Complementing the ontology is a set of guiding principles that govern how data is organized and managed. These principles, often aligned with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) guidelines, ensure data isn't just structured meaningfully but also adheres to established standards. This makes the data discoverable by others, readily accessible for further study, and ultimately reusable for future research endeavours.

The synergy between ontology and principles creates a robust data structure that underpins effective research practices. It empowers researchers to not only capture and store data efficiently but also to extract meaningful knowledge from it. This, in turn, fuels the advancement of scientific and cultural heritage research, leading to groundbreaking discoveries and a richer understanding of our shared past.

The Need for Interoperability Principles in Data Management

The proliferation of heterogeneous data necessitates the adoption of standardized principles to ensure interoperability, enabling seamless data exchange, integration, and analysis across research disciplines and institutional boundaries. Without interoperability, data silos emerge, hindering knowledge discovery, collaboration, and the overall advancement of CH and humanities research.

Challenges of Integrating Heterogeneous CH Data

Integrating heterogeneous CH data represents a complex task, as datasets often exhibit:

- **Varied Formats and Structures:** Data may be stored in diverse formats, such as XML, CSV, JSON, or other proprietary formats, each with its own structure and encoding conventions.

- **Inconsistent Naming Conventions:** Different institutions and projects may employ inconsistent naming conventions for data elements, making it difficult to identify and match corresponding fields across datasets.
- **Uneven Data Quality:** Data quality can vary significantly across datasets, with issues such as missing values, inconsistencies, and errors potentially compromising analysis and interpretation.
- **Evolving Data Standards:** CH data standards may evolve over time, requiring ongoing efforts to adapt and update data management practices to ensure continued interoperability.

The Relevance of data Interoperability for Research, Preservation, and Analysis

Interoperable data is essential for:

- **Advancing Research:** By enabling researchers to combine and analyse data from diverse sources, interoperability facilitates the identification of patterns, trends, and new insights that would remain hidden in isolated datasets;
- **Enhancing Data Preservation:** Interoperable data formats and standardized metadata ensure the long-term accessibility and usability of data, safeguarding it for future generations of researchers;
- **Promoting Scientific Collaboration:** Interoperable data facilitates collaboration among researchers across disciplines and institutions, enabling them to share, exchange, and jointly analyse data to address complex research questions.

In recognition of the ever-increasing importance of data in scientific discovery, we have elaborated a set of principles to guide researchers in effectively structuring their data. These SQARED principles (for which see Section 3.2 SQARED Principles for data structuring), which will be presented in detail throughout this report, address the crucial aspects of data organization, accessibility, and reliability. Clearly defined data structures not only ensure the long-term value and usability of research findings but also facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing within the scientific community.

2. IPERION Ontology

2.1 Modelling a competent ontology for the description of scientific and cultural heritage

The ever-increasing volume of scientific and cultural heritage data presents a significant challenge: ensuring seamless integration and accessibility across diverse sources and formats. This data encompasses a vast array of elements, including physical artifacts, historical documents, architectural marvels, and their digital representations. While this richness offers immense potential for understanding the past, the heterogeneity of data formats hinders effective research and knowledge discovery.

By using a common ontology, the IPERION-HS project wants to establish a standardized system for managing and utilizing scientific and cultural heritage data.

An ontology functions as a formal representation of a specific domain, providing a shared vocabulary and defining the relationships between entities within that domain. In the context of scientific and cultural heritage data, ontology acts as the underlying structure, meticulously defining the relationships between diverse data points. These data points can encompass various aspects of scientific and cultural heritage objects, such as their material composition, stylistic elements, historical context, or geographical location. The ontology ensures that these seemingly disparate elements can be seamlessly integrated, fostering a unified and comprehensive understanding of cultural heritage.

Benefits of Ontologies for Scientific and Cultural Heritage Data

- **Interoperability:** Ontologies enable seamless exchange and integration of data across diverse sources and formats. This fosters collaboration between researchers working in different disciplines, such as archaeologists and art historians, by establishing a common language for describing cultural heritage objects.
- **Accessibility:** By standardizing data representation, ontologies facilitate efficient storage, retrieval, and ultimately, accessibility of cultural heritage information. Researchers can effortlessly locate and utilize relevant data, regardless of its original format.
- **Knowledge Discovery:** Ontologies promote a deeper understanding of scientific and cultural heritage by enabling researchers to explore relationships between different data points. This allows for the identification of patterns and trends that might not be readily apparent when examining data in isolation.

Building a Robust Ontology

Developing a comprehensive and effective ontology is a work that necessarily involves the expertise of domain specialists across the whole process: from design to actual implementation. Archaeologists, art historians, architects, librarians, archivists and other cultural heritage professionals possess a deep understanding of the specific nuances and complexities inherent in their respective fields and source materials. Their involvement is crucial in ensuring that the ontology accurately reflects the intricacies of cultural heritage data.

Standardized vocabularies offer an additional layer of refinement to the ontology. These controlled sets of terms enrich the ontology's precision and enable the capture of finer details within cultural heritage objects and phenomena.

By establishing a shared language and facilitating data integration, ontologies play a pivotal role in the construction of the ontology for cultural heritage data. This robust framework empowers researchers to unlock the full potential of this vast resource, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of our collective past and paving the way for groundbreaking discoveries.

2.1.1 The Parthenos Entities (PE) and Interoperable Research Infrastructure

The Parthenos project's approach to data representation using the PE model¹ establishes a foundation for the SQARED principles. These principles ensure high-quality, reusable, and adaptable data structures in the IPERION HS project. The PARTHENOS data management has been a foundational reference for the development of the SQARED principles used in IPERION-HS.

- **Importance of Knowledge Representation:** PARTHENOS emphasizes the need for an ontological model (PE model) to capture and represent the research process. This aligns with the SQARED principle of **Standardization**, where data structuring follows a defined model for consistency and interoperability.
- **Focus on Core Entities and Relationships:** The PE model prioritizes describing the main entities (dataset, actor, service, software) and their relationships with minimal metadata. This aligns with the SQARED principle of **Quality**, where data focuses on essential information for clarity and efficiency.
- **Lossless Transformation and Provenance:** While some data details might be lost during transformation to the PE model, the core aspects and provenance are preserved. This aligns with the SQARED principle of **Accessibility**, ensuring data retains its meaning and origin for future reference.
- **Mapping and Reusability:** The text mentions the 3M tool² used to map various research infrastructure data models into the PE model. This concept of mapping diverse data formats to a common model promotes **Reuse** of data across different platforms and projects, aligning with the SQARED principle.
- **Evolving Infrastructure:** The text refers to the integration of D-Net³ and 3M into a hybrid data infrastructure. This highlights the importance of adapting and evolving data structures to accommodate new needs, aligning with the SQARED principle of **Evolution**.

¹ Frank Uiterwaal, Franco Niccolucci, Sheena Bassett, Steven Krauwer, Hella Hollander, et al.. From disparate disciplines to unity in diversity How the PARTHENOS project has brought European humanities Research Infrastructures together. International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing, 2021, 15 (1-2), pp.101-116. ff10.3366/ijhac.2021.0264

² 3M - Mapping Memory Manager accessible at: <http://139.91.183.3/3M/>

³ D-Net: <http://www.d-net.research-infrastructures.eu/>

SOURCE ↔		TARGET ↔	
D	./cmd:CMD		PE22_Persistent_Dataset
P	./cmd:MdSelfLink		P1_is_identified_by
R	./cmd:MdSelfLink		E42_Identifier
P	./cmd:MdCreator		P94i_was_created_by
R	./cmd:MdCreator		E65_Creation [create1]
			P14_carried_out_by
R	./cmd:MdCreator		E39_Actor
P	./cmd:MdCreationDate		P94i_was_created_by
			E65_Creation [create1]
			P4_has_time-span
			E52_Time-Span
			P82_at_some_time_within
R	./cmd:MdCreationDate		rdf-schema#Literal
P	./cmd:MdCollectionDisplayName		PP23i_is_dataset_part_of
R	./cmd:MdCollectionDisplayName		PE24_Volatile_Dataset
P	./cmd:MdSelfLink		P129_is_about
R	./cmd:MdSelfLink		E73_Information_Object
P	./cmdp:TextCorpusProfile		PP39_is_metadata_for
R	./cmdp:TextCorpusProfile		PE24_Volatile_Dataset [data1]

Fig.1 In the screenshot we can see the 3M mapping tool used to map data models into PE.

2.1.2 SSHOCro: A Semantic Interoperability Framework for Social Sciences and Humanities

The Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project⁴, funded by the EU, aimed to develop the social sciences and humanities (SSH) domain within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). SSHOC built upon the experience of previous projects like PARTHENOS, with broader participation from key Research Infrastructures (RIs) in the SSH domain. As such it is an excellent basis for the ontology to be built for IPERION-HS

A key outcome of SSHOC was the development of a semantic interoperability framework to manage the diverse data types encountered in SSH research. This framework centers around the SSHOC Reference Ontology (SSHOCro⁵), built upon the existing CIDOC-CRM standard. SSHOCro facilitates data lifecycle management within SSH disciplines, emphasizing event-centric provenance tracking. It enables researchers to document data collection, analysis methods, and research outcomes at each stage.

Formalized within SSHOCro is provenance metadata, crucial for assessing data quality and facilitating resource discovery. The ontology acts as a high-level logbook, documenting validation and reuse workflows for research data. Additionally, SSHOCro promotes data sharing and integration across projects and disciplines by establishing a common language for information exchange.

⁴ SSHOC project: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/>

⁵ SSHOCro: Chrysoula Bekiari, Athina Kritsotaki, Eleni Tsouloucha, & Maria Theodoridou. (2022). D4.20 SSHOCro (final version) (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6771757>

The development of SSHOCro followed a bottom-up approach, informed by real-world research data and structures rooted within the digital humanities and heritage science research domains and supported by the participation on both E-RIHS and DARIAH in the ontology elaboration process. It focuses on capturing the specific research activities, methods, and goals within SSH, considering the research context. This involved identifying workflow patterns and metadata standards through various means, including consultations with SSH data providers and the analysis of existing data repositories.

The focus of the ontology is on practical utility, enabling researchers to create interoperable data pools for reuse. The SSHOCro ontology was used in the context of SSHOC Task 9.4⁶ for the development of the community pilot shared by DARIAH and E-RIHS devoted to the integration of data in Heritage Science and Humanities. SSHOCro prioritizes well-understood concepts for data-driven research in SSH, avoiding overly complex theoretical frameworks. Validation was achieved through case studies, workshops, and community feedback. Overall, SSHOC provides a robust semantic interoperability framework for managing and integrating data within SSH research.

Main Features of the SSHOCro Schema

The SSHOCro schema functions as a specialized extension of the CIDOC CRM, aiming to represent the workflows found in data-driven research, particularly within the SSH and CH domains. It achieves this by modelling concepts as classes and linking them through binary properties. Here's a breakdown of its key features:

Core Structure and Concepts:

- **Event-Centric Approach:** SSHOCro centers around the concept of CIDOC CRM E7 Activity, inheriting its event-centric perspective. This approach emphasizes the documentation of research activities and processes undertaken by researchers.
- **Focus on SSH Research Workflows:** The schema represents the dominant pattern of "collection; preparation and connection; interpretation" frequently observed in SSH and CH research, alongside supporting activities like storage, publication, and information selection.
- **Temporal Entities:** These represent events or processes in time and are all subclasses of E7 Activity, including:
 - **SHE3 SSH Project:** Represents a specific research project.
 - **SHE4 Service:** Encompasses services offered within the research process.
 - **SHE2 Knowledge Workflow Activity:** Represents actions and processes executed in research, with specialized subclasses for data collection, preparation, interpretation, publication, and storage.
- **Endurants:** These represent entities that persist over time and are involved in the activities, categorized as subclasses of E77 Persistent Item:
 - **SHE10 Tool:** Represents tools used in research activities, both physical (e.g., recording devices) and immaterial (e.g., software)
 - **SHE1 Dataset:** Encompasses datasets documented and used in research.

⁶ Cees van der Eijk, Ami Saji, Laura Morales, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Carmen Di Meo, & Francesco Coradeschi. (2021). D9.3 Usability evaluation report (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5783356>

- **SHE11 Method:** Represents methodologies, protocols, and procedures used in research.

Relationships and Properties

- Classes are interlinked by properties such as "consists of", "follows", "produced dataset", "used method", "based on";
- Properties define relationships between classes, capturing the flow of activities, the inputs and outputs of each stage, and the resources used
- Hierarchies of Properties: SSHOCro employs specialized properties and hierarchies to represent the semantics of particular knowledge patterns arising from relevant research questions. For example, it differentiates between a dataset's updated version and a derivative dataset.

Practical Applications:

- **Data Lifecycle Tracking:** Researchers can document primary data collection, preliminary results, final outcomes, and the methods employed at each research stage
- **Validation and Reuse:** Documenting not only research outputs but also the processes behind them allows for validation and potential reuse in other research projects.
- **Resource Discovery:** SSHOCro supports resource discovery by summarizing crucial information about a resource, enabling users to locate relevant information efficiently.

Development and Validation:

- **Bottom-Up Approach:** The schema's development relies on a bottom-up strategy, starting from real-world empirical data and corresponding data structures. It emphasizes the documentation of actual research practices observed in different SSH domains.
- **Informed by Data Structures:** The SSHOCro model is built based on analysis of data structures used in repositories and by direct consultation with data providers.
- **Validated through Mappings and Case Studies⁷:** SSHOCro has been tested and refined through mappings with existing metadata standards (e.g., DDI, CMDI). Its ability to represent real-world research workflows has been validated using case studies from various disciplines.

Naming Conventions:

- **Class Labels:** Identified by numbers with the prefix "SHE" (Social Science and Humanities Entity), followed by a descriptive noun phrase in title case (e.g., SHE3 SSH Project).
- **Property Labels:** Identified by numbers with the prefix "SHR" (Social Science and Humanities Relation), followed by a descriptive phrase (e.g., SHR1 consists of).

⁷ Wolfgang Schmidle, Emanuel Demetrescu, Bruno Fanini, Alberto Bucciero, Alessandra Chirivì, Ivan Ferrari, Francesco Giuri, & Elisabetta Caterina Giovannini. (2022). D5.18 Report on the archaeological case study (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6718970>

The SSHOCro schema, through its structure and features, provides a standardized framework for describing and interlinking research data, promoting interoperability, and facilitating knowledge discovery in the SSH domain.

2.2 IPERION Ontology modelling

Building upon the experiences of past projects (PARTHENOS, RESTORE, SSHOC, H2IOSC), IPERION ontology was deliberately designed as a subset of the combined CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro ontologies. This guarantees its complete compatibility and strict alignment with CIDOC standards. By inheriting the established structure and terminology from these broader ontologies, Hyperion benefits from their well-defined foundations while remaining focused on the specific needs of its domain. In essence, Hyperion strikes a balance between leveraging the strengths of existing knowledge and tailoring it to address the intricacies of its own field.

Mapping of ICCD-OA field elements

XML FIELD	Iperion Ontology
<AUT>	PC14 carried out by P01 has domain E12 Production PC14 carried out by P02 has range E21 Person
<AUTL>info</AUTL>	E21 Person P98b was born E67 Birth P7 took place at E53 Place
<AUTD>info</AUTD>	E21 Person P98b was born E67 Birth P4 has time-span E52 Time span
<AUTX>info</AUTX>	E21 Person P100b died in E69 Death P7 took place at E53 Place
<AUTT>info</AUTT>	E21 Person P100b died in E69 Death P4 has time-span E52 Time span
<AUTU>info</AUTU>	E21 Person P107 is current or former member of E74 Group
<AUTQ>info</AUTQ>	PC14 carried out by P14.1 in the role of E55 Type

<AUTH>info</AUTH>	E21 P1 is identified by E42 Identifier Person
<AUTM>info</AUTM>	E13 Attribute Assignment P140 assigned attribute to E12 Production E13 Attribute Assignment P141 assigned E21 Person E13 Attribute Assignment P2 has type :string
<NCT>	E22 Man Made Object P1 is identified by E42 identifier P2 has type "Codice Univoco del Bene (NCT)"
<NCT><NCTR>info</NCTR>	Parte di NCT
<NCTN>info</NCTN></NCT>	Parte di NCT
<OG><OGT><OGTD>info</OGTD>	E73 Information-Object P2 has type E55 Type
<SGT><SGTI>info</SGTI>	E22 Man-Made Object P62 depicts E1 CRM Entity P2 has type "Identificazione Iconografica"
<SGTT> info</SGTT></SGT>	E73 Information object P1 is identified by E55 Title
<PVC>	E22 Man-made Object P54 has current permanent location :string
<LA>	E22 Human-Made Object P30 transferred custody of E10 Transfer of custody E10 Transfer of custody P28 surrendered by E39 Actor E10 Transfer of custody P29 received by E39 Actor

<PRV>	E22 P49 has former or current E39 Actor	Man-Made Object keeper
<PRC>	E39 P74 has current or former E53 Place	Actor residence
<PRD>	E10 P4 Transfer has of E52 Time-Span	custody time-span
<DTSI>info</DTSI>	E12 P4 has E52 Time-span	Production time-span
<DTSF>info</DTSF>	E12 P4 has E52 Time-span	Production time-span
<CMM>	PC14 carried out by P01 has domain E12 Production PC14 carried out by P14.1 in the role of E55 Type	
<CMMN>info</CMMN>	PC14 carried out by P02 has E39 Actor	range
<MTC>info</MTC>	E22 P45 Man-Made E57 Material	Object of
<MTC>info</MTC>	E22 P108 was Man-Made produced E12 P32 used general E55 Type	Object by Production technique
<MISU>info</MISU>	E54 P91 has E58 Measurement Unit	Dimension unit
<MISA>info</MISA>	E22 P43 Man has Made E54 P90 has xsd:integer	Object dimension Dimension value
<MISL>info</MISL>	E22 P43 Man has Made E54 P90 has xsd:integer	Object dimension Dimension value
<STC>	E22 P44 Man has Made E3 Condition State	Object condition
<STC><STCC>info</STCC></STC>	E3 P2 Condition has :string	State type

<DESI>info</DESI>	E22 P62 E1 CRM Entity	Man	Made	Object depicts
<ISR>	E22 P56 E25 P128 E34 P92i E65 Creation	Man	bears Made	Object feature Feature carries Inscription was brought into existence by
<ISRL>info</ISRL>	E34 P72 E56 Language		has	Inscription language
<ISRS>info</ISRS>	E65 P32 E55 Type	used	general	Creation technique
<ISRT>info</ISRT>	E34 Inscription P2 has type :string			
<ISRP>info</ISRP>	E25 P3 :string	Man-Made	has	Feature note
<ISRI>info</ISRI></ISR>	E34 Inscription P3 has note :string			
<ISRA>info</ISRA>	E65 P14 E21 Person	carried	out	Creation by
<NSC>info<NSC>	E22 P3 :string	Man-Made	has	Object note

Table 1: Mapping of ICCD-OA field elements

Mapping of EAD elements

XML TAG	IPerion Ontology
<c level="X" id=#>	E22 P128 E73 Information Object
<materialspec label="tipologia">	E73 P2 E55 Type
<unittitle>	E73 P1 E35 Title
<title>	E35 P139 E35 Title

<p><container type="numero uno"># <container type="numero sotto"># <container type="inserto"># <container type="busta"># <num type="chiave"># <num type="nuovo ordinamento"># <odd>#</p>	<p>E22 Man-Made Object P1 is identified by E42 Identifier</p>
<p><repository></p>	<p>E22 Human Made Object P54 has current permanent location E53 Place</p>
<p><c level="X" id=#></p>	<p>E22 Human Made Object P92i was brought into existence by E65 Creation</p>
<p><geogname role="luogo"></p>	<p>E65 Creation P7 took place at E53 Place</p>
<p><persname role="tenutario"> <persname role="mano"></p>	<p>E65 Creation P01 has domain PC14 carried out by PC14 carried out by P14.1 in the role of E55 Type PC14 carried out by P02 has range E39 Actor</p>
<p><corpname></p>	<p>E65 Creation P11 had participant E39 Actor</p>
<p><persname> <famname> <corpname></p>	<p>E65 Creation P67 refers to E39 Actor P67.1 type E55 Type</p>
<p><materialspect></p>	<p>E7 Activity P25i_moved_by EL1_Exchange_of_letters EL2_Send_letter #subclass EL1_Exchange_of_letters EL3_Receive_letter #subclass EL1_Exchange_of_letters</p>

<date type="inizio">	EL2_Send_letter P4_has_time-span E52_Time-Span
<geogname type="partenza">	EL2_Send_letter P27_moved_from E53_Place
<person type="mittente">	EL2_Send_letter P01_has_domain PC14_carried_out_by PC14_carried_out_by P02_has_range E39 Actor
<date type="fine">	EL3_Receive_letter P4_has_time-span E52_Time-Span
<geogname type="arrivo">	EL3_Receive_letter P26_moved_to E53_Place
<person type="destinatario">	EL3_Receive_letter P01_has_domain PC14_carried_out_by PC14_carried_out_by P02_has_range E39 Actor
<scopecontent>	E73 Information Object P67 refers to E1 Entity E1 Entity P67.1 type E55 Type
<physdesc>	E22 Human Made Object P3 has note E62 String E62 String P3.1 has type #label
<physfacet type="supporto">	E22 Man Made object P45 consist of E57 Material
<genreform>	E22 Man Made object P3 has note E62 String E62 String P3.1 has type #label
<extent>	E22 Man Made object P43_has_dimension E54 Dimension

<code><dimensions unit="mm"></code> <code><dimensions type="altezza"></code> <code><dimensions type="larghezza"></code> <code><dimensions type="spessore"></code>	E22 Man P43_has_dimension E54_Dimension	Made Made	object object
<code><phystech></code>	E22 P44 E3 E3 P2 E55 Type	Human has Condition Condition has	Made Object condition State State type
<code><note></code>	E73 P3 E62 E62 P3.1 #label	Information has has	Object note String String type

Table 2 Mapping of EAD elements

2.3 Data Mapping and Transformation: Bridging the Gap between Heterogeneous Relational Data and IPERION HS Ontology

2.3.1 Data Mapping

This section presents the role of ontologies in establishing a meaningful semantic representation for transformed data within the IPERION HS framework. Ontologies function as formal knowledge structures, defining domain-specific concepts, properties, and relationships. The IPERION HS ontology serves as the underlying knowledge base for the data transformation workflow. By employing a well-defined ontology and a meticulous mapping process, the IPERION HS framework facilitates the transformation of raw data into a structured and semantically rich format, enabling efficient data analysis and knowledge discovery.

Therefore, the second step in the workflow is crucial for establishing a meaningful semantic representation of the transformed data. Here, the selected relational data elements are meticulously mapped to corresponding concepts within the IPERION HS ontology. This mapping process acts as a bridge, ensuring consistent and accurate translation of the data's underlying meaning into the semantic world of the ontology.

Here are some key aspects of effective data mapping:

- **Relational Data Structure Analysis:** Gain a clear understanding of the structure of the relational data being transformed. This includes identifying tables, columns, data types, and any existing relationships between data elements.
- **Mapping Definition:** Define a mapping scheme that establishes a clear correspondence between relational data elements (columns) and relevant concepts, properties, or classes within the IPERION HS ontology.

- Consider using tools or methodologies like R2RML or SPARQL queries to facilitate the mapping process.
- Ensure the mapping captures all relevant aspects of the data and translates them accurately into the ontology framework.
- **Consistency and Uniqueness:** Maintain consistency throughout the mapping process. The same relational data element should always be mapped to the same concept or property within the ontology.
 - Aim for a one-to-one mapping approach whenever possible to avoid ambiguity in the semantic representation.
- **Mapping Complexity:** The complexity of the mapping process can vary depending on the structure of the relational data and the richness of the IPERION HS ontology.
 - Simple data structures might require straightforward mappings, while more complex data models might necessitate the use of relationships and properties within the ontology.
- **Documentation and Traceability:** Document the mapping process clearly, recording the rationale behind each mapping decision. This documentation will be essential for future reference, maintenance, and potential revisions to the mapping scheme.
- **Class & properties selection:** establishing connections between relational database elements and corresponding ontology classes and properties is a crucial step towards achieving a meaningful and accurate semantic representation of information.

2.3.2 Data Transformation Management

This chapter outlines a workflow for transforming relational data into semantic data, based on the IPERION HS ontology. The workflow is designed to facilitate the integration and analysis of heterogeneous data in the field of cultural heritage science.

Workflow Steps

The workflow consists of six main steps:

Data Selection: Identifying Relevant and High-Quality Data

The initial step of the transformation workflow focuses on selecting the specific portion of relational data that will be converted into semantic format. This selection process requires careful consideration of several factors to ensure successful and valuable data transformation. Here are some key aspects to consider:

- **Relevance to Research Objectives:**
 - Align the data selection with the specific research questions or goals driving the project;
 - Identify data tables or fields containing information directly related to the research focus;
 - Exclude irrelevant or extraneous data that won't contribute to achieving the research objectives (noise removal).

3. Principles

3.1 FAIR Principles

The primary objective of the IPERION ontology framework is to enhance the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of shared data, tools, and resources within the project. Effective data management is essential for research in scientific and cultural heritage, but challenges exist, such as data being scattered across locations, lacking interoperability due to various formats and technological constraints, and having incomplete or missing metadata. To address these challenges, the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles offer a fair practical framework for scientific data management⁸. FAIR principles promote the discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data, enabling researchers to find, use, and combine data from diverse sources more efficiently.

FAIR Principles and Their Importance for Scientific Research

- **Findability:** Data should be easily discoverable for researchers, with accurate and descriptive metadata that facilitates their discovery through search engines and data repositories.
- **Accessibility:** Data should be accessible to anyone with a legitimate interest in using it, with minimal barriers to access, such as licensing restrictions or high costs.
- **Interoperability:** Data should be interoperable, using standard formats and shared vocabularies to enable integration and analysis with other data.
- **Reusability:** Data should be reusable by other researchers, with clear and comprehensive documentation describing how the data was collected, processed, and analyzed.

Adopting FAIR principles offers numerous benefits for scientific research in heritage science and digital humanities:

- **Increased collaboration and knowledge sharing:** By facilitating the discovery and use of data by other researchers, FAIR principles promote collaboration and knowledge sharing within the heritage science community (and beyond).
- **New discoveries and innovations:** Integrating and analysing data from diverse sources can lead to new discoveries and innovations in the field of heritage science. Furthermore the cross-fertilization with other relevant domain could lead to innovative research perspectives due to the removal of technological, domain, language barriers that are responsible for the fragmentation of the digital ecosystem.
- **Cultural heritage preservation and valorisation:** FAIR data can contribute to cultural heritage preservation and valorisation, providing valuable information for the conservation, management, and enjoyment of cultural assets.

Strategies for Making Cultural, Scientific and Heritage Data FAIR Compliant

⁸ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

To make scientific and cultural heritage data FAIR compliant, several strategies need to be implemented:

- **Develop shared standards and vocabularies:** It is essential to develop shared standards and vocabularies for describing, formatting, and managing scientific and cultural heritage data.
- **Implement accessible data repositories:** scientific and cultural heritage data should be deposited in accessible and interoperable data repositories, with appropriate access policies and licenses.
- **Promote documentation and metadata:** Researchers should be encouraged to accurately document their data and provide comprehensive and descriptive metadata.

The implementation of a data management workflow incorporating standardized data transformation aligns with ontologies like the IPERION Ontology (inheriting from CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro). This approach ensures adherence to the FAIR principles by promoting findability through consistent metadata structures, accessibility via open-format repositories, interoperability through the adoption of shared vocabularies, and reusability by facilitating clear data understanding through well-defined ontological frameworks and possibility of extracting data from the tools incorporated into the platform.

3.2 SQARED Principles for data structuring

The effective utilization of data is contingent upon its organization, accessibility, and reliability. To address these challenges, the SQARED Data Structuring Principles have been established to guide researchers in structuring their data in a standardized, high-quality, reusable, and evolving manner, ensuring its long-term value and accessibility.

The SQUARED acronym encompasses five key principles:

- **Standardization**
- **Quality**
- **Accessibility**
- **Reuse**
- **Evolution**
- **Documentation**

3.2.1 Standardization

Standardization is crucial for ensuring consistency within and across different datasets. This means adopting common and recognized data structures, ontologies and models, such as (domain) standards or open file formats. Using shared standards facilitates the integration of data from diverse sources and simplifies analysis and visualization.

Strengths:

- Promotes data consistency and interoperability across systems and applications;

- Facilitates data integration and analysis from heterogeneous sources;
- Reduces data redundancy and storage requirements;
- Enhances data exchange and collaboration among researchers.

Rationale for Adoption:

Standardization ensures that data is structured in a uniform and predictable manner, making it easier to understand, use, and share. This is particularly important in collaborative research environments where data needs to be exchanged and integrated from multiple sources.

3.2.2 Quality

High-quality data is essential for obtaining reliable (i.e. repeatable and comparable) scientific results. Data quality should be assessed and improved through data validation, verification, and cleaning processes. This includes identifying and correcting errors, handling missing values, and verifying the internal consistency of the data.

Strengths:

- Enhances the reliability and trustworthiness of research findings;
- Improves the efficiency and effectiveness of data analysis;
- Reduces the risk of errors and misinterpretations;
- Promotes data integrity and (long-term) preservation;

Rationale for Adoption:

High-quality data is the foundation of credible research. By implementing data quality assessment and improvement processes, researchers can ensure that their data is accurate, consistent, and complete, leading to more reliable and trustworthy results.

3.2.3 Accessibility

Data accessibility is critical for maximizing the value of information. When data is easily discoverable, understandable, and usable, researchers can leverage its full potential. This principle fosters collaboration across disciplines by ensuring that everyone speaks the same "data language". Accessible data also accelerates scientific progress by allowing researchers to quickly find relevant datasets and integrate them into their work, ultimately leading to new discoveries and a deeper understanding of the world around us.

Strengths:

- Enhances building on existing knowledge for solid research;
- Allows researchers from different fields to collaborate and exploit data for new discoveries;
- Reuses existing data to save time, money, and resources;
- Enables transparency to build public confidence in science and its applications.

Rationale for Adoption:

Data accessibility isn't just about sharing information, it's a strategic investment. Open data fuels collaboration across disciplines, sparking innovation. Transparency builds public trust in science and its applications. Accessible data maximizes its value by allowing reuse in new studies, saving time and resources. Finally, institutions that champion open data practices enhance their reputation and attract top talent, solidifying their place at the forefront of scientific progress.

3.2.4 Reuse

Data should be structured to facilitate its reuse for various research, analysis, and preservation purposes. Utilizing open data formats and permissive licenses allows other users to freely access, use, modify, and share the data, with proper attribution. This promotes collaboration and innovation within the research community.

Strengths:

- Maximizes the value of data by enabling its (re)use for multiple purposes;
- Facilitates knowledge discovery and innovation across research disciplines;
- Promotes open science and collaboration within the research community;
- Accelerates research progress and reduces duplication of effort.

Rationale for Adoption:

Data reuse is essential for maximizing the return on investment in data collection and curation efforts. By structuring data in a reusable manner and adopting open data policies, researchers can make their data accessible to others, enabling new discoveries and collaborations.

3.2.5 Evolution

Data is constantly evolving and needs to be updated and maintained over time. Mechanisms for managing data changes and updates should be implemented, while ensuring the consistency and accuracy of the information. This includes documenting changes made to the data and creating processes for migrating to new data versions.

Strengths:

- Ensures that data remains relevant and up-to-date over time;
- Facilitates adaptation to changing research needs and technologies;
- Promotes data integrity and long-term preservation;
- Enhances the credibility and trustworthiness of research findings.

Rationale for Adoption:

Data is dynamic and needs to evolve to reflect changes in research questions, methodologies, and technologies. By implementing mechanisms for data versioning and change management, researchers can ensure that their data remains relevant, accurate, and accessible over time.

3.2.6 Documentation

Clear documentation is essential for transparency and reproducibility of research. Documentation should describe in detail the data collection, transformation, and integration methodologies, as well as the data structures and formats used. Comprehensive documentation facilitates the understanding and reuse of data by other users.

Strengths:

- Enhances the transparency and reproducibility of research;
- Facilitates data understanding and interpretation for other researchers;
- Promotes data integrity and (long-term) preservation;
- Encourages data reuse and collaboration within the research community.

Rationale for Adoption:

Comprehensive documentation provides essential context and understanding for data users, both present and future. By clearly documenting data collection, transformation, and integration processes, researchers can ensure that their data is accessible, interpretable, and reusable, promoting open science and collaboration.

4. Conclusions

The adoption of the IPERION-HS ontology and the SQUARED principles for data structuring presents a significant step forward in fostering a robust and collaborative research environment within the scientific and cultural heritage domain. By leveraging the IPERION-HS ontology's domain-specific vocabularies and adhering to the SQUARED principles' emphasis on discoverability, accessibility, reusability, and engagement, researchers can ensure the creation of a reliable, accessible, and reusable data ecosystem:

Standardization: Use unified, widely acknowledged data structures, ontologies, and models (including industry standards or open formats) to ensure consistency.

Quality: Attain error-free high-quality data through validation, verification and cleaning processes which take care of missing values; errors; inconsistency.

Accessibility: Display data prominently for easy discoverability, comprehensibility and usability — making it more valuable and encouraging cooperation.

Reuse: Create reusable data artifacts meant for different research or analysis purposes alongside preservation strategies using open formats plus permissive licenses.

Evolution: Set up a mechanism for managing the changes to the dataset— such as updates, versioning and change control— so that the stored information is always useful over time.

Documentation: Write a detailed document explaining how data was collected, transformed or integrated with methodology descriptions about the structures and formats used.

The adoption of the IPERION-HS ontology and the SQUARED principles also paves the way for the development of innovative prototypes that will be described in Deliverable 5.6, as tangible demonstrations of the effectiveness of this approach, showcasing its ability to address real-world challenges in cultural and scientific heritage research.

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Table 1 Mapping of ICCD-OA field elements, pag. 12

Table 2 Mapping of EAD elements, pag. 16

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science
HS	Heritage Science
CENDARI	Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure
CIDOC-CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
DARIAH-IT	Italian national node of Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH-ERIC)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
E-RIHS.it	Italian national node of the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
ERIC	European Research Infrastructures Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PARTHENOS	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RI	Research Infrastructure
S&CI	Social and Cultural Innovation
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
SSHOCro	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud Reference Ontology

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